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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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RECOGNISING CORPORATE ZAKAT UNDER NIGERIAN CORPORATE LAW AS A MEANS OF ALLEVIATING POVERTY IN NORTH-EASTERN NIGERIA

By
Shamsuddeen Magaji*

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria is blessed with natural and mineral resources but, the country is still rated high in poverty. The country recently emerged out from an insurgency caused by Boko Haram (an insurgent group that killed thousands and displaced millions of people in the Northeastern part in the name of acclaimed religion). Evidence suggests a nexus between the Boko Haram insurgency and extreme poverty in the Northeast region. Part of the objective of this research is to explore how amendment to the current Companies Income Tax Act Cap C21 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 and the Finance Act 2020 in Nigeria could enhance the involvement of private corporations in alleviating poverty in Nigeria since the Nigerian government has unsuccessfully created programs to alleviate poverty. The study is socio-legal involving face-to-face interviews with 10 respondents that include selected company directors, religious leaders, and relevant Sharia agencies among others. The findings indicate that the Companies Income Tax Act and Finance Act should incorporate provisions that will recognise some form of tax credit or tax break to private corporations involved in issuing corporate Zakat as a religious obligation on Muslims in order to organize and motivate their contributions to Centres or Commissions for poverty relief because one of the side effects of poverty is fuelling the success of terrorist groups such as Boko Haram.

Keywords: *Boko Haram, corporate Zakat, poverty, tax break, tax holiday*

1. INTRODUCTION

What are the legal ways through which private corporations can be involved in alleviating poverty in Nigeria, especially in the Northeast region affected by insurgency? Despite being blessed with natural and mineral resources; Nigeria is still rated high in poverty.¹ The country recently emerged out of the insurgency caused by *Boko Haram* (an insurgent group) in the Northeastern part. There is a nexus between the *Boko Haram* insurgency and extreme poverty in the Northeast region.² Part of the objective of this research is to explore how amendment to the current Companies Income Tax Act Cap C21 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 and the Finance Act 2020 could enhance the involvement of private corporations in alleviating poverty in Nigeria.

Although the Nigerian government has unsuccessfully created programs to alleviate poverty,³ nevertheless tax credit should be given to private corporations by the government in order to organize and motivate their contributions to centres for poverty relief because one of the side effects of poverty is fuelling the success of terrorist groups like *Boko Haram*.⁴

The first part of this paper discusses the negative impact of poverty as one of the root causes of the *Boko Haram* insurgency in North-eastern Nigeria as the focus is on northern Nigeria (North-east in particular) followed by the various initiatives set up

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¹ Qasim, Mustapha Isa. "The Role of Zakat in Poverty Alleviation in Nigerian Society." In *Kertas kerja, 1st Kedah International Zakat Conference, Lembaga Zakat Negeri Kedah, Kedah*, vol. 6. 2020.

² Odalonu, Boris Happy, and Eberechukwu Faith Obani. "Poverty and the Challenges of Security in the North-Eastern Region of Nigeria: A Case Study of Boko Haram Insurgency (2009-2017); Elomien, Emmanuel, Victor Jubril, Olumuwiwa Ajavi, and Sheriff Folarin. "Insurgency and Extreme Poverty: Evidence from the Boko Haram Crisis in Northeast Nigeria." *Covenant University Journal of Politics and International Affairs* (2022).

³ Kolawole, Roseline J. "Evaluation of Poverty Alleviation Programmes in Nigeria: The Demand Driven Approach Perspective." *International Journal of Development and Management Review* 16, no. 1 (2021): 161-177; Gidighi, Matthew O. "Assessing the impact of poverty alleviation programs on poverty reduction in Nigeria: Selected programs." *Poverty & Public Policy* 15, no. 1 (2023): 76-97.

⁴ Ugonna, Ogbu. "Poverty and Violence in Nigeria Implication on Democracy." (2022).

by the government to eradicate poverty and how the initiatives failed.⁵ The second part studied the concept of *Zakat* (alms-giving) as one of the 5 pillars of Islam which is obligatory on every Muslim that satisfied the threshold of *nisab*⁶ for *Zakat*. The third part examines the involvement of private corporations in corporate social responsibility and payment of *Zakat* and how amendments can be made to the extant company and tax law in Nigeria to encourage corporations that are giving *Zakat* through tax exemption or tax relief.

The research focuses on how amendment to existing law especially the Companies Income Tax Act Cap C21 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 and the Finance Act 2020 could enhance the involvement of private corporations in alleviating poverty in Nigeria. Section 11 of the Finance Act 2020 which amends section 25 of the Companies Income Tax Act made provisions for tax deductions in respect of companies that made donations to any fund set up by the Federal or state government or their agencies in respect of any natural disaster, pandemic or other exigencies as allowable deductions. This deduction is with respect to cost of production, manufacturing or any other purpose which evidence must be presented to the relevant tax authorities. The research is socio-legal and adopts a qualitative methodology. The data consists of library-based materials as well as empirical data using semi-structured interviews with respondents across selected private corporations, relevant government agencies; selected government officials; and Islamic scholars. The data from the interview was coded and grouped into themes and sub-themes while the analysis was conducted using thematic analysis based on the themes that emerged from the interview. On the one hand, the library-based data was analysed based on content analysis. The research suggests for an amendment to the existing Companies Income Tax Act and the Finance Act 2020 to enhance the involvement of private corporations in alleviating poverty in Nigeria.

2. BOKO HARAM INSURGENCY

⁵ Taiwo, J. N. "Problems and Prospects of Poverty Alleviation Programmes in Nigeria." *International Journal of Business and Management Review* 4, no. 6 (2016): 18-30.

⁶ The minimum amount or value that every Muslim must possess before being obliged to pay *Zakat* of 2.5% of his/her total wealth which is a kind of redistribution of wealth among the community

Boko Haram is an insurgent group in Nigeria that declared war against the government and is determined to disrupt the social setting by all possible means, especially through violence.⁷ The group disliked democracy and sought to destroy the existing system of governance in Nigeria, believing that democracy and western-style education are directly opposite to the ideals and beliefs of an Islamic state.⁸ The group was also not interested in any kind of peaceful dialogue with the state⁹ and were bent on fighting to the logical end. They weakened the machinery of government until they were ultimately contained by the state.¹⁰ To Sambo Dasuki, former National Security Adviser, "*Boko Haram seek to force fundamental changes on society, operating with impunity; they violate all decent human values in an effort to draw a commensurate response from authorities.*"¹¹ According to Nigeria's former Chief of Defense Staff (General Martin Luther Agwai), "*you can never solve any of these problems (Boko Haram) with military solutions ... it is a political issue; it is a social issue; it is an economic issue; and until these issues are addressed, the military can never give you a solution.*"¹²

The solution to *Boko Haram* is beyond the use of military power, it involves a socio-economic perspective by providing opportunities and incentives for people to improve their livelihood.¹³ This further reiterates the need for the government to be tactical in trying to bring an end to the insurgency. The focus of this research is not rather to delve into the issue of *Boko Haram* insurgency as a whole but at least to proffer a solution to addressing poverty as one of the root causes of the insurgency in Northeast Nigeria.

3. BOKO HARAM AND POVERTY

⁷See Andrew Walker, United States Institute of Peace, What Is Boko Haram (2012), <https://www.usip.org/publications/2012/05/what-boko-haram> in : The Challenges of Subduing Insurgency in Restive and Dysfunctional Societies: Lessons from Nigeria's Experience with Boko Haram, 30 Tul. J. Int'l & Comp. L. 281, 282

⁸ See Alex Thurston, the Brookings Project on U.S Relations with the Islamic World, "The Disease is Unbelief: Boko Haram's Religious and Political Worldview 5 (2006) [hereinafter The Disease is Unbelief] ("Boko Haram's ideology is often described as comprising two stances: opposition to democracy and rejection of Western-style education.").

⁹ Felix Akpan et al., *Boko Haram and the Counter-Terrorism Policy in Nigeria*, 10 CAN. SOC. SCI. 151, 153 (2014).

¹⁰ See Amy Pate, *Boko Haram: An Assessment of Strengths, Vulnerabilities, And Policy Options* 31-32 (2015).

¹¹ Mohammed Dasuki Sambo, *Challenges of Governance in the Era of Insurgency*, Sahara Reporters (Aug. 10, 2014), <http://saharareporters.com/2014/08/10/challenges-governance-era-insurgency-mohammed-sambo-dasuki#.WeVNEs-MJdg.email>.

¹² Max Siollum, *How Boko Haram Can be Defeated*, New African Mag. (Jan. 19, 2015), <https://newafricanmagazine.com/9615/>.

¹³ Adewunmi J. Falode, *Countering the Boko Haram Group in Nigeria: The Relevance of Hybrid Doctrine*, Small Wars J. (2017), <https://smallwarsjournal.com/jrnl/art/countering-the-boko-haram-group-in-nigeria-the-relevance-of-hybrid-doctrine-0>

The *Boko Haram* insurgency has caused the deaths of thousands of people,¹⁴ displaced millions of people and destroyed public structures in the Northeast region which is already affected by poverty.¹⁵ There is a strong correlation between poverty, financial hardships and *Boko Haram* insurgency. In other words, poverty and, financial hardships were among the root causes of the *Boko Haram* insurgency because people are becoming more susceptible to manipulation by the insurgents who usually promise a better life to anyone who joins the group.¹⁶ The percentage of the population in the Northeast that is living below the poverty level is almost twice or thrice the rate in the southern part of Nigeria and therefore calls for the effort of government to alleviate poverty.¹⁷

There is also the argument that the Federal Government has long neglected the Northeast region. This long-standing neglect has left vast majority of citizens poor, uneducated, and enraged. The feelings of alienation, maltreatment, and injustice are deep and pervasive. There is possibility that, unless these problems are addressed, the Northeast region may remain violent, unsafe, and home to insurgents who would continue to express their dismay and dissatisfaction with the federal government.¹⁸ At this juncture, one may be interested to know the efforts or initiatives put in place for alleviating poverty in Nigeria which would be discussed in the next subheading.

4. EFFORTS OF THE NIGERIAN GOVERNMENT IN ALLEVIATING POVERTY

The Nigerian government has ratified various treaties, covenants and charters that seek to protect the rights of its citizens like the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR); the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR); the African [Banjul] Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights

¹⁴ Paul Carsten and Felix Onuah, "Northeast Nigeria Insurgency Has Killed Almost 350,000 - UN", *Reuters*, 24 June 2021, available at: <https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/northeast-nigeria-insurgency-has-killed-almost-350000-un-2021-06-24/>.

¹⁵ Tosin Osasona, The question of definition: Armed banditry in Nigeria's North-West in the context of international humanitarian law *International Review of the Red Cross (UK)* Apr 01, 2023 *International Review of the Red Cross*, Volume 105 Number 923 April 2023 pp. 735-749.

¹⁶ Okechukwu Oko: The Challenges of Subduing Insurgency in Restive and Dysfunctional Societies: Lessons from Nigeria's Experience with Boko Haram (2022) 30 *Tul. J. Int'l & Comp. L.* 281.

¹⁷ J. PeTer Pham, The Afr. Ctr. For Strategic Stud., *Boko Haram's Evolving Threat* 7 (2012), <https://africacenter.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/ASB20EN-Boko-Haram's-Evolving-Threat.pdf>.

¹⁸ PaTricio Asfura-Heim & Julia Mcquaid, *Diagnosing T=the Boko Haram Conflict: Grievances, Motivations, and Institutional Resilience in Northeast Nigeria* 66 (2015).

(ACHPR) among others. However, the practical implementation is still in question.¹⁹ Relevant to mention here is the injunction of the World Conference on Human Rights to the effect that, "the existence of widespread extreme poverty inhibits the full and effective enjoyment of human rights," this makes it more imperative for "immediate alleviation and eventual elimination" of poverty as a priority.²⁰

There are several initiatives set up by the federal, state government and not-for-profit organisations intending to alleviate or eradicate poverty in Nigeria but these initiatives have failed to achieve the desired goal and instead of alleviating poverty; these initiatives are turned into an avenue for stealing the resources due to corruption²¹ or sometimes due to a lack of political will from the government.²² Arguably, poverty alleviation initiatives or policies put in place focused more on growth, provision of basic needs and rural development. Even though there is a reduction in the poverty level, but the poor still get poorer because the most vulnerable people are not targeted by such initiatives.²³ For example, in the year 2000, Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP) was introduced by the Federal government which was substituted with National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) in 2001. NAPEP focused on poverty eradication through the Capacity Acquisition Programme (CAP) which emphasised skills acquisition and training for self-reliance. However, the initiative failed for lacking seriousness from the government.²⁴ Again, the *Youth Empowerment Program (YEP) on poverty reduction and national development introduced by the Nigerian government did not provide the desired result because of the high rate of unemployment in the country.*²⁵ So also other initiatives.

¹⁹ Philip C. Aka, Bridging the Gap Between Theory and Practice in Humanitarian Action: Eight Steps To Humanitarian Wellness In Nigeria, 24 Willamette J. Int'l L. & Dispute Res. 1 (2016).

²⁰ Vienna Declaration & Program of Action, P 1, U.N. Gen. Assembly, World Conference on Human Rights, Jul. 12, 1993, A/CONF.157/23, Endorsed by Gen. Ass. Res. 48/121, Dec. 20, 1993, <http://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/Vienna.aspx>

²¹ Taiwo, supra note 1.

²² Zain, Zarina Mohd, Nor Suhaiza Md Khalid, Suzei Mat Nurudin, and Timothy Onimisi. "Poverty alleviation policies in Malaysia and Nigeria: A review." *Environment-Behaviour Proceedings Journal* 6, no. 16 (2021): 239-246.

²³ Kolawole, Roseline J. "Evaluation of Poverty Alleviation Programmes in Nigeria: The demand driven approach perspective." *International Journal of Development and Management Review* 16, no. 1 (2021): 161-177.

²⁴ Sule, Babayo, Umar Adamu, and Muhammad Aminu Yahaya. "National Poverty Eradication Programme in Nigeria (NAPEP): A Case Study of Capacity Acquisition Programme (CAP) in Gombe State 2003-2015." *Journal of Public Administration and Governance* 9, no. 2 (2019): 230-247.

²⁵ WAZIRI, MUSA, and Abu Idris. "Youth Empowerment Program in Nigeria: A strategy for poverty alleviation and national development." *Journal of Public Value and Administrative Insight* 2, no. 3 (2019): 12-14.

According to statistics from the National Bureau of Statistics, over 133 million Nigerians are multi-dimensionally poor. To limit this, the Federal and state governments must develop effective policies to harness the country's resources to create jobs and wealth. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended that inhibits the states and creates a domineering centre needs to be amended to set free the states' huge potential.²⁶ This calls for a holistic approach to the problem with a view to look for alternative initiatives to the problem of poverty alleviation especially as it relates to curtailing the resurgence of Boko Haram especially through legal and religious approach. Part of the alternatives in this research is to examine the role of Zakat (almsgiving) as a religious obligation in Islam and the need to involve private corporations in donating either as a religious obligation or as corporate social responsibility to alleviate poverty in Northern Nigeria while in return such corporations would be given some tax-breaks or holiday by the relevant laws (Companies Income Tax and the Finance Act).

5. ZAKAT (ALMSGIVING) AS ONE OF THE FIVE PILLARS OF ISLAM

The word "Zakat" traced its origin from the Arabic word "Zakah" which means to grow and to increase with other meanings including *cleanliness, growth, blessing and praise*". In Islamic law, the word *Zakat* refers to a specific share of wealth prescribed by Allah (SWT) to be distributed among the categories of those entitled to receive it.²⁷ The inner soul of a person who pays *Zakat* becomes better and his wealth becomes pure. A verse of the Holy Quran provides; "Take *Zakat* from their wealth to purify and cleanse them".²⁸ Payment of *Zakat* out of one's wealth to give to the poor is a fundamental act of *Ibadah* in Islam (worship) because it is an act of obedience to Allah (SWT). Muslims were commanded to pay *Zakat* from their wealth in the second year of the Hijrah (migration) of the prophet Muhammad (SAW) from Mecca to Medina. In this regard, the Qur'an provides: "And establish regular prayer and give *Zakat* and bow down your heads with those who bow down (in prayer)."²⁹

²⁶ <https://punchng.com/eradicating-poverty-in-nigeria-an-urgent-task/> (accessed April 13, 2024).

²⁷ Al-Qardawi, Yusuf. *Poverty and its solution in Islam*. Adam Publishers, 2004.

²⁸ Qur'an Chapter 9 verse 103.

²⁹ Qur'an Chapter 2 verse 43.

The significance of giving *Zakat* cannot be overemphasised. From this verse of the Qur'an; *Zakat* comes next after prayers to show its significance. Any Muslim who meets the threshold of nisab (minimum amount of wealth required to pay *Zakat*) is obliged to give *Zakat*.³⁰ The main essence of giving *Zakat* is to act as a kind of wealth redistribution among the community and as a form of poverty alleviation. One would be interested to know that, there are now arguments that since corporate legal personality is recognised in Islam; then corporations that are owned by Muslims should be obliged to pay *Zakat*. Even if one would assume that corporate *Zakat* is not recognised; then, private corporations have a role to play through their corporate social responsibility.

State laws and public organizations, such as those in Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Pakistan, and Malaysia, regulate and enforce *Zakat*. There are certain parallels in the discourse around *Zakat* payment compliance, especially in regulated *Zakat* systems. Even though the nature, tenets, and goals of *Zakat* and tax are very different, according to tax compliance literature. The legal ramifications of some financial planning strategies that lower the amount of tax owed are one of the factors that set *Zakat* compliance apart from tax compliance. While tax-paying practices are generally accepted as lawful, they may be unethical and wrong from a Shari'ah standpoint.³¹

6. CORPORATE PERSONALITY FROM ISLAMIC LAW PERSPECTIVE

There are arguments as to whether corporate personality is recognised under Islamic Law. The Arabic word "*shirkah*," also known as "*musharakah*"³² refers to corporate organizations. In its broadest definition, it describes the blending of assets that constitute capital, such that it is impossible to tell one asset from another. This means that since both the business and the person running it are viewed as one and the same, there is no distinction made under Islamic law between a company and a partnership

³⁰ Abdullahi, Shafiu Ibrahim. "Zakat and Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria: an analytico-longitudinal study." *Available at SSRN 4064720* (2022).

³¹ Sawmar, Abdulsalam Ahmed, and Mustafa Omar Mohammed. "Enhancing zakat compliance through good governance: a conceptual framework." *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance* 13.1 (2021): 136-154.

³² Abd Ghadas, Zuhairah Ariff, and Hartinie Abd Aziz. "Analysis on the Doctrine of Limited Liability under Company Law and Shari'ah." *Al-Shajarah: Journal of the International Institute of Islamic Thought and Civilization (ISTAC)* 24, no. 2 (2019): 293-310.

enterprise.³³ However, there is disagreement among jurists over the existence of this concept. According to Abd Ghadas, the concept of corporate personality originated with the concept of "artificial person," or "shakhsiyah I'itbariyah."³⁴

Modern jurists like Mustafa Ahmad al Zarqa and Muhammad Abu Zuhrah maintained that Islamic institutions like waqf (trust) and bait al mal (Islamic treasury), which are acknowledged in Islam as artificial bodies, are the source of the concept of artificial entity.³⁵ The jurists went on to say that "al-dhimmah" argument might justify the doctrine that acknowledged artificial entities. This phrase is used to settle disputes involving ability and duty. The jurists claimed that this theory dates back to the period *of the holy prophet* (S.A.W), who is credited with saying: The (lives of all Muslims are equal, they are one band against others; the lowest of them can guarantee their protection).³⁶ The idea of corporate legal identity as it exists in English law, however, is not the same in Islamic law. The English Law's equating of al-dhimma with the artificial personality principle has been questioned by jurists such as al Bazdawi and al Nawawi. They contended that something that is not genuine could not be bound by the sharia. Whatever the case, some jurists believed that Islamic law recognized the concept of a distinct legal institution. They have the similar relationship to the establishments that the prophet (SAW) knew, such as the Waqf (Endowment/Charitable Trust), Masjid (Mosque), Baitul mal (Islamic Treasury), Joint Stock, and so on.³⁷ The jurists argued that waqf is a religious and legal institution in which an individual donates a portion of his property to a charity or philanthropic cause, so establishing a distinct legal entity.³⁸

Companies established with mutual consent, in which one or more parties consent to operate for profit to share profit and losses as agreed, are approved by the *Sunnah* (traditions of the Prophet) and *Ijma'* (the consensus of the authorities in Islam).³⁹ In

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ *Ibid.*

³⁵ Zuhairah Ariff Abd, Ghadas, Nasarudin Abdul Rahman, and Halyani Hassan. "Shari'ah Corporation': the legal entity of corporation from the Malaysian law and Shari'ah perspective." *International Journal of Liability and Scientific Enquiry* 6, no. 4 (2013): 232-246.

³⁶ Zuhairah, Ghadas, Nasarudin and Halyani op cit.

³⁷ Zuhairah, Ghadas, Nasarudin and Halyani op cit.

³⁸ *Ibid.*

³⁹ Nicholas H.D., "Islamic Perspectives on the Law of Business Organisations II: The Sharia and Western-style Business Organisations," *European Business Organization Law Review* (2010) 11: 273-307.

one hadith (ascribed to God), stating: "I am the third (partner) of every two partners, unless one of them deceives the other, in which case I shall dissociate Myself from them"; and by the tradition that Usamah ibn Shurayk came to the Prophet, God bless him and grant him salvation, asking: "Do you know me?" The Prophet (SAW) answered: "How can I not know you, when you were my partner and the best partner, never deceiving nor quarrelsome!" In addition, the Prophet was sent to the people during a period when they had established corporations, and he approved of their actions without raising any objections or prohibitions. One of the tenets of Sunnah is that it becomes permissible. As for the consensus (of authorities *in* Islam), Muslims have traded as partners from the beginning of Islam, and no one has ever objected.⁴⁰

7. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND CORPORATE ZAKAT

CSR is an avenue for corporations to carry on business ethically. Now, apart from the main object of making profit; corporations tend to contemplate other stakeholders including the society they operate.⁴¹ It is evident that a corporation which promotes social equality and enjoys a good reputation has a chance to attract more value to its products.⁴² Corporations now engage in various forms of philanthropic gestures and donating to society by meeting rising community expectations,⁴³ in order to promote the idea that the society is of great concern to them. It would be incorrect to minimize the influence of companies. Nowadays, corporations hold social positions. At the moment, corporations make up more than half of the top 100 economic entities in the world.⁴⁴ The belief that firms have a duty to tackle socio-ecological issues is essentially linked to one's perspective on corporate responsibility. It is evident that the law confers powers of a natural person to a corporation, making it an "artificial person". The law makes this position distinctive. It gives the company, a non-living thing, the

⁴⁰ N. Saleh, *The General Principles of Saudi Arabian and Omani Company Laws (Statutes and Shari'a)* (Namara Publications 1981); see also Chapter 1 and the Koranic verses (Al-Baqara II:220; Al-Kahf XVIII:19; Saad XXXVIII:24; and Al-Zumar XXXIX:29)

⁴¹ Sharma, Eliza. "A review of corporate social responsibility in developed and developing nations." *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* 26, no. 4 (2019): 712-720.

⁴² Abrantes Ferreira, D., Gonçalves Avila, M., & Dias de Faria, M., Corporate social responsibility and consumers' perception of price. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 6(2) (2010) 208–221. <https://doi.org/10.1108/1747111011051720>

⁴³ Singh, Kuldeep, and Madhvendra Misra. "The evolving path of CSR: toward business and society relationship." *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences* 38, no. 2 (2022): 304-332.

⁴⁴ Peter French, *Collective and Corporate Responsibility* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1984) at ix.

natural powers and ability to operate in our world as though it were a person.⁴⁵ Corporate *Zakat* is viewed as one of the good instruments of alleviating poverty⁴⁶ which is the focus of this study.

Relevant to mention here is section 11(9) of the Finance Act which provides for a maximum of 10% allowable deductions on the assessable profits after deductions for any company that made donations to funds set up by federal, state or their respective agencies to cater for natural disaster, pandemic or other exigencies. This provision is a clear indication that with necessary interest from government, similar or related provision can be incorporated under the Finance Act and the Companies Income Tax Act to provide some tax break, exemption or allowance for companies that pay corporate *Zakat*. Having discussed about various related subheadings, the next subheading reflects the views of various respondents.

8. DATA ANALYSIS

In this study, 10 respondents were interviewed face to face from Bauchi, Yobe and Maiduguri on whether corporate *Zakat* will help in alleviating poverty in the Northeast region especially concerning *boko haram* insurgency. All the respondents were unanimous in their opinion that corporate *Zakat* will greatly assist in curtailing the resurgence of *Boko Haram* in the Northeast region. The respondents equally argued that there is a strong nexus between poverty and the *Boko Haram* insurgency. However, while some of the respondents maintained the view that corporate *Zakat* obtained from various companies may be channelled through Sharia or *Zakat* Commission in various states in order to distribute same to the targeted beneficiaries, others argued that the companies should channel their *Zakat* directly to the needy in their respective states of operation in the region.

According to Respondent 1, “unless we want to maintain the current system where government initiatives on poverty alleviation are failing, we have to look beyond giving *Zakat* to government institution for distribution. I am of the view that our laws should be amended to give incentives through tax break to companies that give certain

⁴⁵ John Micklethwait & Adrian Wooldridge, *The Company: A Short History of a Revolutionary Idea* (Toronto, ON: Random House Inc, 2003) 4 at xvii; Jeffrey Bone, Legal Perspectives on Corporate Responsibility: Contractarian or Communitarian Thought? 24 *Can. J.L. & Juris* (2011) 277.

⁴⁶ Andriani, Andriani, and Mairijani, Mairijani. "Strengthening Corporate Zakat Policy in Indonesia." *Iqtishadia* 12, no. 1 (2019): 58-73.

threshold as corporate *Zakat*.” Respondents 3 & 4 equally maintained the same opinion. However, Respondent 5 opined that, “I have no reservation if corporate *Zakat* are being paid or channelled through Sharia or *Zakat* Commission provided these Commissions will live up to their expectations while taking into account the purpose of giving out *Zakat* to the needy in the region as a means of countering the resurgence of *Boko Haram* insurgents.

Respondent 6 on his part argued that, “it is going to be a wonderful initiative if companies will begin to give out corporate *Zakat* to the needy. However, it should be borne in mind that the legislation that will try to recognise this has to equally contemplate the penalty that will be imposed for failure to pay corporate *Zakat* by a company. This is because, *Zakat* to every Muslim that has the financial means is mandatory as a religious obligation. In fact, one of the 5 pillars of Islam.” In the same vein, Respondents 7 & 8 maintained the same view and argued that, “companies should be encouraged to pay corporate *Zakat* not just because the man-made law has made provision for that but recognising that it is equally a religious obligation”.

In their response, Respondents 9 & 10 argued that, “introducing corporate *Zakat* under our company and tax law will be a fantastic idea but there may be some challenges, one of which concerns a situation where a company is not fully owned by Muslims. The challenge will be that, non-Muslim shareholders who are not under religious obligation to pay *Zakat* may find it difficult to allow their resources being paid as a corporate *Zakat*. Notwithstanding, some non-Muslims may agree provided that the money will be used to impact the life of the needy persons as a kind of corporate social responsibility. Incorporating some tax incentives under the Companies Income Tax Act and the Finance Act would greatly assist”.

From the perspective of government, Respondent 10 argued that, “while I have no reservation if our Companies and Allied Matters Act and the Finance Act or any relevant legislation may be reviewed to recognise corporate tax just like the way Islamic banking is recognised, government will always look at the advantage or otherwise of introducing corporate *Zakat* in exchange for tax break or tax holiday for companies that pay. But what is obvious is that, government has been investing so much resources in an attempt to alleviate poverty and more so, we will never wish to

see the resurgence of the Boko Haram insurgency. In essence, there is great advantage in recognising corporate *Zakat*.”

One of the Respondents bewailed that *Zakat* remained discretionary due to lack of legal framework for the collection of *Zakat* in Nigeria whereas many rich Muslims that ought to have paid *Zakat* avoid paying same leaving meagre sum that is not adequate to make reasonable impact on the country.

Speaking at a workshop titled “Maximising the Power of *Zakat* to Support Families Forced to Flee in Nigeria,” organised by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), Muhammad Maidoki (Chairman of Association of *Zakat* and Waqf Operators in Nigeria) stated that Nigeria is in a tough time economically. He noted that with a legal framework for *Zakat*, billions of Naira could be realized annually that would be channeled in providing developmental needs of the nation. *Zakat* could be used in providing for the very poor, orphans, widows and aged persons. There is the need for legal framework at both the federal and state levels, maintaining that there is also the need for a unified framework for *Zakat* collection and distribution.⁴⁷

9. FINDINGS

The findings in this study indicate that there is a nexus between poverty and Boko Haram insurgency that ravaged the Northeastern part of Nigeria. The Nigerian government has made several efforts to alleviate poverty which to some extent have failed. On the one hand, government’s effort in countering Boko Haram insurgency has significantly resulted in eliminating the group. However, for fear of their resurgence, there is the need to have a different approach of alleviating poverty and countering the resurgence of *Boko Haram*. To this end, this study finds that, recognising corporate *Zakat* under Nigerian corporate and tax law could have positive effect in alleviating poverty and countering the resurgence of *Boko Haram*

10. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that subsequent research should focus on corporate *Zakat* by public companies, although, there may be some challenges especially for public companies with a large number of shareholders with

⁴⁷<https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2022/04/07/govt-asked-to-provide-legal-framework-for-collection-of-zakat> (accessed 21/2/2024).

different faith apart from Islam. Further research may equally explore other parts of the country though, there are different causes of poverty in the two regions.

11. CONCLUSION

The devastating effect of poverty in Nigeria especially in the Northeastern part cannot be quantified. Evidence suggests a nexus between poverty and the Boko Haram insurgency that ravaged the Northeastern part. Although there is a great success in countering the insurgency, the Nigerian government has made several efforts to eliminate poverty, which is believed to be one of the root causes of the Boko Haram insurgency, in order to prevent its resurgence. There is the need to involve companies in paying corporate *Zakat* which is also a religious obligation for Muslims that meets the financial requirement. Section 11(9) of the Finance Act provides for a maximum of 10% allowable deductions on the assessable profits after deductions for any company that made donations to funds set up by federal, state or their respective agencies to cater for natural disaster, pandemic or other exigencies. This provision is a clear indication that with necessary interest from the government, similar or related provision can be incorporated under the Finance Act and the Companies Income Tax Act to provide some tax break, exemption or allowance for companies that pays corporate *Zakat*.

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